

Nodifloretin-A New Flavone from *Lippia Nodiflora*

A. K. Barua,¹(Miss) P. Chakrabarti and P. K. Sanyal

Lippia nodiflora (family *Verbenaceae*) is a creeping perennial herb and is valued as a febrifuge and diuretic¹. From the leaves of this plant, Joshi and Bakuni^{2,3} reported the isolation of two compounds, nodiflorin A and B.

L. nodiflora (whole plant) has been re-examined in this laboratory. The alcoholic extract of this plant has been found to contain a mixture of flavonoid compounds. By preparative paper chromatography it has been possible to isolate a new flavone called nodifloretin, in poor yield, and in an amorphous state. All attempts to crystallise it has so far been unsuccessful. It was however found to be homogeneous in paper chromatography. The molecular weight of nodifloretin could not be determined by mass spectrometry because it decomposed in the ionizing chamber. Its molecular formula $C_{16}H_{12}O_7$, was determined on the basis of mass spectral studies of its tetra ethyl (Id) and tetramethyl ether (Ib). Methoxyl group estimation indicated the presence of one methoxyl group in nodifloretin. It gave red colour with magnesium and hydrochloric acid. Its u.v. spectrum [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 351 (Band I), 282 and 234 $m\mu$ (Band IIa and IIb)] is very typical of flavones having hydroxyl or methoxyl substituents at both 3' and 4' positions⁴. The u.v. spectrum of nodifloretin showed bathochromic shifts [λ_{max} 375, 315 (inflection), 276 (inflection) and 242 $m\mu$] of both bands I and II when studied in presence of sodium acetate thereby showing the hydroxyl groups at both 4' and 7' positions to be free. The u.v. spectrum of nodifloretin taken after the addition of a few drops of aluminium chloride solution [λ_{max} 370, 295, 258 (inflection) and 238 $m\mu$] showed bathochromic shift of both the bands, thus suggesting the presence of a free hydroxyl group at C-5. When the spectrum was studied in presence of boric acid and sodium acetate [λ_{max} 350, 289 and 238 $m\mu$] there was bathochromic shift of band II but band I remained unaffected indicating the presence of *o*-dihydroxyl group in ring A and absence of the same in ring B. As it was shown earlier that the 4'-hydroxyl group is free, there must be a 3'-methoxy group in nodifloretin. Nodifloretin gave positive Bargellini test^{5,6} which is characteristic of flavones containing 5 : 6 : 7 or 3' : 4' : 5' : tri-hydroxy groups. On the basis of the above spectral analysis the structure of nodifloretin appeared to be (Ia).

Treatment of nodifloretin with ethereal diazomethane furnished a tetramethyl ether (Ib), $C_{20}H_{20}O_7$, m.p. 177–78° (M^+ 372) and a trimethyl ether (Ic), $C_{19}H_{18}O_7$, m.p. 192–94° (M^+ 358). The tetramethyl ether of nodifloretin [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 325, 266 and 240 $m\mu$] was identified

1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal plants", C. S. I. R., 1956, p. 155.
2. B. C. Joshi and D. S. Bakuni, *J. Sci. and Ind. Research* (India), 1959, **18B**, 525.
3. B. C. Joshi, Astr., the 54th session, Indian Sci. Congress, 1966. P. 161.
4. L. Jurd, "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", Ed. T. A. Geissman, 1962, p. 110.
5. G. Bargellini, *Gazz. Chim. ital.*, 1919, **49**, 47.
6. G. B. Marini-Bettolo and A. Ballio, *Gazz. Chim. ital.*, 1946 **76**, 410.
7. K. Venkataraman, "The Chemistry of Flavonoid Compounds", Ed. T.A. Geissman, 1962, p. 74.

as 5 : 6 : 7 : 3' : 4'-pentamethoxy flavone⁸ (Ib) by direct comparison (m.p., mixed m.p., t.l.c. and u.v. spectra) with an authentic sample. The u.v. spectrum of the trimethyl ether [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 340 (Band I), 279 and 242 $m\mu$ (Band II)] showed characteristic bathochromic shift of band I and band II [λ_{max} 360, 292 and 260 $m\mu$] when studied in presence of aluminium chloride indicating the presence of a free hydroxyl group at C-5. Further treatment of the trimethyl ether with ethereal diazomethane furnished the tetramethyl ether (Ib). The trimethyl ether should therefore be 5-hydroxy-6 : 7 : 3' : 4'-tetramethoxy flavone (Ic).

Tetraethyl ether (Id) of nodifloretin, $C_{24}H_{28}O_7$, m.p. 150–51.5°, [λ_{max}^{EtOH} 329, 267 and 241 $m\mu$] was prepared by treatment of nodifloretin with ethereal diazoethane. Its mass spectrum showed the molecular ion peak at m/e 428 and a strong peak (base peak) at m/e 399 due to the ion a formed by loss of an ethyl group from the 6-ethoxy group⁹. Hydrolytic fission¹⁰ of the tetraethyl ether (Id) furnished *m*-methoxy-*p*-ethoxy benzoic acid, m.p. 194–96°. On the basis of the data presented above, nodifloretin may be represented as 5 : 6 : 7 : 4'-tetrahydroxy-3'-methoxy flavone.

Besides nodifloretin, a glucoside, $C_{35}H_{58-60}O_6$ m.p. 278–84° (decomp.) was also isolated from the ethanolic extract. It showed a single spot in t.l.c. and formed an acetate m.p. 162–64° which also showed a single spot in t.l.c. Acid hydrolysis of the glucoside furnished glucose, β -isosterol and stigmasterol. Therefore the glucoside isolated by us is a mixture of glucosides of β -isosterol and stigmasterol. It has not been possible to resolve the above mixture.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. S. M. Sircar, Director and Prof. A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute for their interest in this work. Thanks are due to Prof. T. A. Geissman, University of California, for an authentic sample of 5 : 6 : 7 : 3' : 4'-pentamethoxy flavone. One of us (P.K.S.) is grateful to C.S.I.R. for the award of a junior research fellowship. Mass spectra of the compounds were kindly recorded by Dr. B. C. Das (C.N.R.S., France) and Dr. K. G. Das (National Chemical Laboratory, Poona).

Department of Chemistry
Bose Institute
Calcutta-9

Received February 6, 1969

8. I. E. Gillet and T.A. Geissman, *Angew. Chem.*, 1957, **69**, 679.
9. J. H. Bowie and D. W. Cameron, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 1632.
10. K. Venkataraman, "The Chemistry of Flavonoids" Ed. T. A. Geissman, 1962, p. 83.